

ROLE OF ASYMMETRIC DIMETHYLARGININE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

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Resumetable

The results of numerous studies in recent decades confirm the critical role of the vascular endothelium in the regulation of vascular homeostasis. A criterion for assessing the functional state of the endothelium is endothelium-dependent vasodilation, regulated by nitric oxide (NO). Despite clinical and experimental evidence of the relationship between increased plasma ADMA levels and the development of cardiovascular events, the clear etiopathogenetic role of ADMA in CVD requires further research. In order to accurately answer the question of whether ADMA is an etiological factor or a biological marker of CVD, additional analysis aimed at studying the biochemical, genetic and pharmacological aspects of ADMA metabolism is required, the results of which are presented in this article.

Key words: myocardial infarction, endothelial dysfunction, asymmetric dimethylarginine, risk factors.

Introduction. Asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) is an endogenous competitive inhibitor of endothelial NO synthase (eNOS) and is currently considered as a generally accepted marker of endothelial dysfunction by most researchers. In vitro experiments have shown that ADMA inhibits endothelium-dependent relaxation of arteries, increases the level of indicators characterizing the degree of oxidative stress in endothelial cells, in particular, enhances the synthesis of superoxide anion radical by endothelial cells. These molecular mechanisms, activated by increasing ADMA concentrations, cause the development of various dysfunctions of the cardiovascular system, which gave grounds to consider the ADMA level as a criterion and risk factor for the development of CVD. Thus, ADMA plays a key role in the development and progression of CVD associated with a spectrum of diseases and pathological conditions characterized by impaired NO production. In recent years, there has been increased interest in asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. As a structural analogue of L-arginine, ADMA inhibits the activity of all isoforms of nitric oxide synthase (NOS), causing disruption of the mechanisms of nitric oxide formation in blood plasma and tissues. In 1992, it was first shown that increasing ADMA concentrations resulted in a significant

reduction in nitric oxide production [1]. Nitric oxide is known to play an important role in the regulation of vascular tone, and subsequent studies have established a strong correlation between plasma ADMA levels and the incidence of cardiovascular events [2]. To date, more than 800 experimental and clinical studies have been published on ADMA metabolism and the role of ischemic development in cardiovascular disease.

ADMA in blood plasma. Under physiological conditions, ADMA concentration in blood plasma ranges from 0.3 to 1.4 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ [3]. Masuda et al. calculated that the intracellular concentration of ADMA in the endothelial cells of the rabbit carotid artery is 5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ [4]. Faraci et al. showed that the addition of ADMA at a concentration of 2 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ to brain lysates is sufficient to reduce NOS activity by 50% [5]. Taken together, these data indicate that the concentration of ADMA in endothelial cells is sufficient for ADMA to play a role in the regulation of endothelial nitric oxide production in vivo.

ADMA level in cardiovascular diseases. Elevated ADMA levels have been found in a wide variety of cardiovascular diseases, including coronary artery disease (CHD). Currently, IHD is the leading cause of death in industrialized countries. According to recent studies, elevated plasma ADMA levels have been observed in association with risk factors for CAD such as hypercholesterolemia [6], hypertension [6-7], type 2 diabetes mellitus, and insulin resistance [8].], hypertriglyceridemia [9], hyperhomocysteinemia [10], chronic renal failure [11]. Increased ADMA concentration in blood plasma was identified in patients with myocardial infarction in comparison with the control group [12]; Several clinical studies have shown a direct relationship between mortality after myocardial infarction and plasma ADMA concentrations, independent of other traditional risk factors [13]. One prospective study found that plasma ADMA levels were elevated in patients with coronary artery disease compared with healthy controls, and unstable angina was accompanied by a significantly more pronounced increase in ADMA levels than stable angina [14]. The Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health Study, a large prospective study with a mean follow-up of 5.5 years, documented that plasma ADMA concentrations are associated with cardiovascular and all-cause mortality in patients with stable and unstable angina, regardless of known risk factors [15].

Prospects for further research. ADMA is a new cardiovascular risk factor associated with a spectrum of clinical situations characterized by impaired nitric oxide production. Despite clinical and experimental evidence of the relationship between increased plasma ADMA levels and endothelial dysfunction and the risk

of cardiovascular complications, the causal role of ADMA in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular diseases has not yet been proven. To answer the question of whether ADMA is a marker of cardiovascular disease or an etiological factor, a comprehensive biochemical, genetic and pharmacological approach is required.

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